

WHOLODANCE

Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education

Call identifier: H2020-ICT-2015 - Grant agreement no: 688865

Topic: ICT-20-2015 - Technologies for better human learning and teaching

Deliverable 8.1

Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan and preliminary materials

Due date of delivery: March 31st, 2016

Actual submission date: April 14th, 2016

Start of the project: 1st January 2016

Ending Date: 31st December 2018

Partner responsible for this deliverable: LYNKEUS

Version: 4.0

D8.1 - Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan and preliminary materials	WhoLoDancE - H2020-ICT-2015 (688865)
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Dissemination Level: Public

Document Classification

Title	Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan and preliminary materials
Deliverable	D8.1.
Reporting Period	1
Authors	Stefano Di Pietro, Mirko De Maldè, Edwin Morley-Fletcher
Work Package	WP8
Security	PU
Nature	Report
Keyword(s)	Dissemination strategy, exploitation, dissemination materials, website, infographic.

Document History

Name	Remark	Version	Date
Stefano Di Pietro	First draft with preliminary material	1.0	March 15 th
Stefano Di Pietro	Second version	1.1	March 25 th
Mirko De Maldè	First revision of the document	1.3	April 3 rd
Stefano Di Pietro	Second version with latest dissemination preliminary material	2.0	April 5 th
Mirko De Maldè	Final Revision and Submission	3.0	April 6 th

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Introduction

This document outlines the strategy for the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and the relevant plan and principles followed by the WhoLoDancE consortium. It also provides some preliminary communication materials, which have been produced for an early start of these activities.

As explained in the DoW, WhoLoDancE's outcomes have the potential of raising great interest for a variety of different artistic and technological research communities, ranging from Dance Companies and Dance Institutions to Researchers and Scholars, as well as to European industry.

The core principle that WhoLoDancE will follow to ensure the effectiveness of its dissemination and communication activities, around which the entire work on these areas will be developed, is to make easily understandable, from the very beginning, the visionary aim of the project, and to engage a significant number of final end-users and stakeholders. To ensure an early engagement of the end-users is also ensured, the dance institutions within the Consortium will play a key role.

1. The overall strategy

The WhoLoDancE Consortium conceived a unifying strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation, taking into account and trying to maximise the potential of cross-fertilisation between these activities, fostering the combined effects of general communication, delivery of specific peers'-driven messages, and ultimately the presentation to the general public and potential end-users of advanced products and services. These activities will be performed continuously during the project, with a focus on communication at the very beginning, then dissemination of the results to peers (e.g. relevant tech and dance experts), and the exploitation of these results, mainly (but not exclusively) in the form of products and services ready for commercialisation.

In performing the above-mentioned activities, the WhoLoDancE Consortium will adopt the best practices identified by the EC¹, such as defining the key audiences, preparing specific messages for each of them, engaging the stakeholders also to contribute to the Action. Furthermore, the Consortium will define, and continuously refine, the key messages of the project, and will carefully choose the most effective means of communication and dissemination, according to both audience and specific content to be delivered.

Furthermore, WhoLoDancE will make extensive use of social networks and social media with a particular focus on Twitter and Vimeo that have been identified as the most effective social tools to raise interest in the target audiences of the project.

WhoLoDancE will produce photos and video clips that will be shared via social network and the project's website that will show parts of the project activities.

Two different videos will be produced for each relevant organised event/meeting, each one targeted on a different audience, aiming at reaching the diverse audiences of the project with specific contents and languages:

1. *Project Video Teaser*, targeted on a wide audience of interested public
2. *Technical Report Video*, which will include detailed data of the experimental sessions to raise the interest of scholars, researchers and professionals.

¹ European Commission, *Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants*, 25 September 2014. Available online: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

Finally, two audiences of stakeholders will be addressed from the very beginning of the project: dancers and choreographers.

As explained in the scheme below, Communication activities are mainly meant to raise the interest of the different stakeholders, and to engage end users and receive feedback for the implementation. To this end, the preliminary activities will be intended to identify the key messages: concepts and goals, identify the key audiences and prepare preliminary general materials. The ultimate goal of the Peer-based dissemination of results consists in providing a clearly understandable outreach to all main outcomes, whatever the view-point from which to look at them, be it either technical, or related to a learning or teaching perspective.

Finally, leveraging on the network effect activated with both dissemination and communication, the exploitation activities will be specifically devoted to foster the market potential of products/solutions to be offered to the end-users, while taking into account different applications for the developed technologies and services.

In order to do so, the exploitation plan will be finalised to getting a proper understanding of the market, identifying key products and solutions, defining IPRs management, and conceiving the most effective marketing strategy for each product/service and specific market.

In performing these activities, the WhoLoDancE consortium will leverage on the playful-entertainment potential of the proposed solutions, and their subsequent media-attractiveness.

Particular attention will be devoted to the organisation of workshops and other dissemination events. As already explained in the Description of Work, WhoLoDancE will organise specific workshops at the Dance companies' premises, to demonstrate the results, engage the intended end-users, and gather useful feedback for further refining the results.

At the end of the project, a major dissemination event will be represented by the WhoLoDancE "Dance-athon", which will bring together dance professionals from around Europe and, thanks to the dancers involved in the project, will highlight the project results through high-impact big demo-live show.

Consistently with such an approach, WhoLoDancE has already organised a number of dissemination activities: the project was already presented at the *Digital Echoes Conference*, held at Coventry University on

March 4th; a second opportunity will be on April 28th 2016, when the project will be presented at the *Accademia Nazionale di Danza* in Rome, Italy.

Finally, the project's team already submitted a paper for the *MOCO 2016* conference, that will be held on 5-6 July 2016 in Thessaloniki, where also a specific WhoLoDancE workshop has been additionally scheduled for the 7th and 8th of the same month, and a project meeting is set for the 4th and 5th (see for more details the relevant section 1.3. Dissemination events).

A central role will be played by the foreseen experimental workshops to be held in Coventry, Thessaloniki and Genoa, and at the participating dance companies' premises.

The preliminary dissemination activities will be put at the service of the successful organisation of this event, striving to raise awareness, among all stakeholders, about the project's methodology, objectives and overall vision.

As already mentioned in paragraph 1.1, an effective communication strategy must be based upon correctly identifying the messages, and the target audiences and media, to be used. Clearly aiming at doing so, WhoLoDancE dissemination will be organised and the content delivered, making use of a number of different tools, capable of jointly determining appropriate a synergy and interaction in the usage of the different media and formats:

- **Demos of the developed tools** for showcases in international Innovation fairs around Europe
- **Video clips and HD photos** to present highlights of the consortium's work
- **Posters and brochures in different version** targeted for different audiences and formats
- **WhoLoDancE Web site**, with a dedicated channel for distribution of "Dissemination Objects" (DO's) and a Press release section including the relevant information and Dissemination Material for the Press translated in the national languages of the member of the consortium
- **Twitter account**, using it not only to disseminate the WhoLoDancE materials, but also as a link to the dancers community, by sharing the content of other projects and activities related to Dance and Technology
- **Vimeo account** where the video material will be shared
- **Seminars and workshops** at relevant conferences in the area
- **Regular newsletter** to interested communities and stakeholders;
- **Scientific Papers**, describing Wholodance's results to all relevant international scientific journals

1.1. Principles and Best Practices

Wholodance's dissemination and communication activities will follow the following principles and best practices, already proved to be effective within a number of currently ongoing EC-funded projects (e.g. MD-Paedigree, Cardioproof, Health-e-Child, Sim-e-Child in particular) that will be refined and tailored to the specific characteristics and needs of the project:

- **A bi-directional and knowledge sharing approach will be adopted**, to capitalise the interaction with the intended end-users, and to ensure the final usability of the technological solutions. To this end, a process of feedback and interactions has been conceived, based on the workshops and other communication and dissemination events that will be organised by the Consortium.
- **Given the diversity of the potential stakeholders interested in the outcomes of the project, specific messages will be conceived and tailored to each audience**, organising communication and dissemination activities, materials and channels for each target audience;
- To maximise the effectiveness of the communication activities, in particular oriented to the general public and non-expert stakeholders, the team in charge of dissemination and exploitation will pay particular attention in **making us of everyday language** rather than in an academic or industrial language.
- **In order to expand the network of reference and widen the community of stakeholders, the Consortium will aim at facilitating the involvement of further institutions and centres** in the initiative, expanding the base of data and knowledge in the consortium, and **establishing good collaboration with other relevant projects**
- **The dance companies will be involved in the dissemination and communication activities**
- **In order to leverage on WhoLoDancE's media-attractiveness and entertainment potential**, the key dissemination events will include **dance performance and live demonstration of the implemented technical solutions.**
- **Make extensive use of multimedia content** to explain in the most effective way the approach and outcomes of the Project

1.2. WhoLoDancE messages

Five different core WhoLoDancE objectives have been identified, in view of maximising the potential of raising interest in the project's wide and diverse communities of end users.

The key project's objectives and targeted audiences are briefly described below:

1. **Investigate bodily knowledge** by applying Similarity search tools, computational models, emotional content analysis and techniques for the automated analysis of non-verbal expressive movement to dance data that will help investigate principles, vocabularies, mental imagery and simulation connected to Dance Practises.

The main targets of the outcomes of this objective will be scholars in the field of Psychology, Linguistics, Knowledge Representation, HSS in general, and all the scholars involved in the study of Dance and the Performing Arts in general.

2. **Preserve the Cultural Heritage** by creating a proof-of-concept of a motion capture repository of dance motions built in a method allowing interpolations, extrapolations and synthesis through similarity search among different compositions documenting diverse and specialized dance movement practices.

The main targets of the outcomes of this objective will be scholars and researchers in the field of History and Cultural Studies with interest in Dance Practices but also Virtual Reality Experts and Professional as well as Dance students and interested public that want to deepen their knowledge of dance practices.

3. **Innovate the Teaching of Dance** by developing life-size volumetric display that will enable a dance student to literally step inside the Dance master's body that through the use of immersive and responsive motion capture data, will Identify and respond to collisions between the physical and virtual bodies.

The main targets of the outcomes of this objective will be Dance Students and Teachers as well as Researchers in the field of Virtual Reality and Technology applied to Dance and Art in general.

4. **Revolutionise Choreography** by building and structuring an interactive repository of motion capture dance libraries. Custom dance data blending engine will give choreographers and dance teachers a powerful tool to blend and assemble an infinite number of dance compositions.

The main targets of the outcomes of this objective will be Choreographers, Dance Teachers, as well as Contemporary and Multimedia Artists in general.

5. **Widen the access and practice of Dance** by providing access to the created dance database through commercially available consumer electronics motion capture devices like the MS Kinect, Intel's real sense and others

The outcomes of this objective will have the potential of interesting a wider audience than the former ones, being not limited do dance professionals and students, but oriented towards raising interest among the general public, with a particular focus on younger generations making use of Educational Games, centred on basic WhoLoDancE learning principles.

1.3. Dissemination events

At the time of writing, WhoLoDancE has already participated to the *Digital Echoes Conference* in Coventry University on March 4th (pictures below) and will participate and present a project presentation in the prestigious *Accademia Nazionale di Danza* in Rome on April 28th on the occasion of the International Dance Day.

Whole-body interaction learning for dance
education WhoLoDancE #DES16 #DES2016
@CDaRE_CU

Wholodance's team has organised the networking events (as scheduled in the table below) and submitted a paper to the International Conference "MOCO 2016" that will be held in Thessaloniki on July 5th – 6th 2016. Below the abstract of the submitted paper:

ProjectName: Towards a methodology for selecting Motion Capture Data across different Dance Learning Practices

ABSTRACT

In this paper we present the objectives and preliminary work of ProjectName, a European project, aiming at using new technologies for capturing and analyzing dance movement to facilitate whole-body interaction learning experiences for a variety of dance genres. Dance is a diverse and heterogeneous practice and ProjectName will develop a protocol for the creation and/or selection of dance sequences drawn from different dance styles for different teaching and learning modalities. As dance learning practice lacks standardization beyond dance genres and specific schools and techniques, one of the first project challenges is to bring together a variety of dance genres and teaching practices and work towards a methodology for selecting the appropriate shots for motion capturing, to acquire kinetic material which will provide a satisfying proof of concept for Learning scenarios of particular genres. The four use cases we are investigating are 1) classical ballet, 2) contemporary dance, 3) flamenco and 4) Greek folk dance.

Preceding the MOCO conference, a General WhoLoDancE consortium meeting will take place in Thessaloniki on 4th and 5th July, and on 7th and 8th July a WhoLoDancE Workshop will also take place, with an expected attendance of dancers and interested public.

On June 6th to 10th, another workshop opened to the interested public will take place in parallel with the Eyes Web Week in Genoa, providing WhoLoDancE with a first opportunity for experimenting with the public the workshops that will take place again with wider audience in Greece in parallel with the MOCO conference. Below the Agenda of the event in Genoa:

5th EyesWeb Week

The EyesWeb Week is an intensive tutorial aiming at sharing with participants the experience of the Casa Paganini - InfoMus Research Centre in the EyesWeb project. The main focus is on the EyesWeb XML open software platform (freely available [here](#)) for scientific and technological research and development of innovative multimodal interfaces, systems, and applications (including distributed and mobile apps) in a growing number of fields, such as therapy and rehabilitation, independent living, artistic production, active experience of cultural heritage, and education.

Download the PDF version of the **Announcement** [here](#)

A particular focus will be on the on-going H2020 EU - ICT Projects at Casa Paganini

- **ICT TELMI** (H2020-ICT-2015): Technology Enhanced Learning of Musical Instrument Performance
Learning to play a musical instrument is mostly based on the master-apprentice model in which the student's interaction and socialization is often restricted to short and punctual contact with the teacher followed by long periods of self-study resulting in high abandonment rates. In such a learning model, modern technologies are rarely employed and almost never go beyond audio and video recording.
The main aim of the TELMI project is to study how we learn musical instruments, taking the violin as a case study, from a pedagogical and scientific perspective and to create new interactive, assistive, self-learning, augmented-feedback, and social-aware systems complementary to traditional teaching
- **ICT WhoLoDance** (H2020-ICT-2015): Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education
The work is in the framework of the EU Horizon2020 ICT Project WhoLoDance. It consists of the development of computational models and of algorithms for the analysis in real-time of non-verbal human behaviour. The analysis is based on non-verbal full-body multimodal signals. The research will be in the framework of the Workpackage WP2 (Multimodal sensing and capturing analysis) and WP3 (Semantic and emotional representation models).
- **ICT DANCE** (IA, 2015-2017): investigating how affective and relational qualities of body movement can be expressed, represented, and analyzed by the auditory channel.

Dissemination opportunities and Network/Community Building for *WhoLoDance*

Dissemination opportunity	Location	Time of the conference	Submitted Material
Digital Echoes	Coventry University	4 th March 2016	Coventry did an oral presentation.
Athens Science Festival	Athens -Greece	6 th - 10 th April 2016	Athena will present the project
International Dance Day	Accademia Nazionale di Danza (Rome)	28 th April	Lynkeus will do an Oral Presentation
MOCO 2016	Thessaloniki-Greece	5 th - 6 th July 2016	Collective Paper Submitted: "Towards a methodology for selecting Motion Capture Data across different Dance Learning Practices"
Special issue of Computational Culture	Call for abstract		
5th EyesWeb Week	University of Genova	6 th – 10 th June 2016	
CID 44th International World Congress on Dance Research	Athens -Greece	29 th June -3 rd July 2016	Athena will submit an abstract for presentation.
Europeana Space Final Conference	Berlin	November 2016	
DRHA 2016 Digital Research in the Humanities and Arts	University of Brighton	4 th - 7 th September 2016	Coventry will submit an abstract
Laval Virtual	Laval (FR)	March 2017	
International Dance and Somatic Practices Conference	Coventry University	7 th – 9 th July 2017	

A clear acknowledgement of EC funding will be included in all dissemination activities on any media or event as per Article II.30 of the grant agreement and in compliance to the Communication guidelines for projects.

1.4. Dissemination Material

1.4.1. Wholodance logo

1.4.2. Project Website

During the first month of the project, the first version of the project website (www.wholodance.eu) has been released online. The latest version of the website has been released on March 31st.

Different features of the website have been developed organized around three main principles that make the website particularly innovative:

1. **High level of responsiveness** of all the different sections of the website. Each object in the website interacts and respond to the scrolling on the mouse on the screen
2. **Different navigation options:** from the most simple and intuitive that include only the core concepts of the project to a more traditional menu where more details about the project can be explored.
3. **Content organization via Keywords:** The project description is organised by keywords that are connected to tags within the website. By clicking on any keywords on the interactive tagcloud placed on the main page but also on the sidebar of every page of the website, it is possible to reach all the pages of the website related to the selected keyword.

The layout of the responsive main page it is organized as follow:

- **Responsive Landing Page** with a short cut to the About Section
- **An About section** which include the five main objectives of the project as listed in the Wholodance messages' section.
- **A Navigable and interactive tagcloud** connected to the content within the website.
- **An Explore Wholodance Section** where a preview of the twitter and Vimeo is available and show the recent post and videos on the selected social accounts.
- **A SlideShow** of the best graphic content related to the project
- **A Consortium section** with the link to partner's website
- **A footer connected to the ec.europe twitter account**
- **A Contact section**

The Menu of the website placed on top of the page it is organized as follow:

- **Home**
- **Project Description**
 - **About Wholodance**
 - **Main Objectives**
 - **Investigate bodily knowledge**
 - **Preserve the Cultural Heritage**
 - **Innovate the Teaching of Dance**
 - **Revolutionize Choreography**
 - **Widen the access and practice of Dance**
 - **Project Timeline**
- **Media**
 - **Photo**
 - **Video**
 - **Audio**
- **Events**

- Consortium
- Press Kit
 - Press Release
 - English
 - Italiano
 - Espanol
 - Français
 - Media Kit
- About

At this point of the project, some sections are still under construction and the structure of the site will evolve as necessary during the life of the project.

1.4.3. Photos and Videos

A professional photographer will be involved in the major WhoLoDancE events.

During the Experimental Capture Session in Genoa on March 21st - 23rd the first photo shots have been taken with the aim of documenting the process and producing dissemination material. Below some photos of the Session held at Casa Paganini in Genoa:

Marianne Masson from K.Danse on stage during the Experimental Capturing Session in Casa Paganini (Genoa,IT)

University of Genoa's Team placing sensors on dancer Muriel Romero from Stocos during the Experimental Capturing Session in Casa Paganini (Genoa,IT)

Jean.Marc Matos, Choreographer and Director of K.Danse dance company, following the capturing process during the Experimental Capturing Session in Casa Paganini (Genoa,IT)

The videos, both the *Project Video Teaser* and the *Technical Report Video*, are currently being edited and in the post-production process, and will soon be ready, for the approval of all partners.

1.4.4. Project Poster

Two different layouts of the poster have been developed and tailored for different audiences and formats.

The one below will be used for poster presentations at conferences, technology fairs and dance performances normally printed in A3 format or bigger.

WHOLODANCE
Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education

Starting Date: January 1st, 2016
Duration: 36 months
Total EU Contribution: € 3.332.585,00

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ACTION FUNDED UNDER THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 PROGRAMME

Wholodance aims at developing and applying breakthrough technologies to Dance in order to:

- 01 Investigate body knowledge** by applying similarity search tools, computational models, emotional content analysis and techniques for the automated analysis of non-verbal expressive movement to dance data that will help investigate principles, vocabularies, mental imagery and simulation connected to Dance Practices.
- 02 Preserve the Cultural Heritage** by creating a proof-of-concept motion capture repository of dance motions built in methods allowing interpolations, extrapolations and synthesis through similarity search among different compositions documenting diverse and specialized dance movement practices.
- 03 Innovate the Teaching of Dance** by developing life-size volumetric display that will enable a dance student to literally step inside the Dance master's body that through the use of immersive and responsive motion capture data, will identify and respond to collisions between the physical and virtual bodies.
- 04 Revolutionize Choreography** by building and structuring an interactive repository of motion capture dance libraries. Custom dance data blending engine will give choreographers and dance teachers a powerful tool to blend and assemble an infinite number of dance compositions.
- 05 Widen the access and practice of Dance** by providing access to the created dance database through commercially available consumer grade motion capture devices like the MS Kinect, Intel's real sense and others.

Wholodance has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 688865

CONSORTIUM

LYNKEUS, ATHENA, MOTEK, POLITECNICO MILANO 2012, Peachnote, Coventry University, UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI GENOVA, Kdanse

The second version of the Poster can be used in different formats (e.g. A4) due to the different font size of the text and delivered also as brochures to the interested public at any event with different target audiences:

WHOLODANCE
Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education

Starting Date: January 1st, 2016
Duration: 36 months
Total EU Contribution: € 3.332.585,00

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ACTION FUNDED UNDER THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 PROGRAMME

WHOLODANCE AIMS AT DEVELOPING AND APPLYING BREAKTHROUGH TECHNOLOGIES TO DANCE IN ORDER TO:

- 01** INVESTIGATE BODILY KNOWLEDGE by applying Similarity search tools, computational models, emotional content analysis and techniques for the automated analysis of non-verbal expressive movement to dance data that will help investigate principles, vocabularies, mental imagery and simulation connected to Dance Practises.
- 02** PRESERVE THE CULTURAL HERITAGE by creating a proof-of-concept motion capture repository of dance motions built in methods allowing interpolations, extrapolations and synthesis through similarity search among different compositions documenting diverse and specialized dance movement practices.
- 03** INNOVATE THE TEACHING OF DANCE by developing life-size volumetric display that will enable a dance student to literally step inside the Dance master's body that through the use of immersive and responsive motion capture data, will identify and respond to collisions between the physical and virtual bodies.
- 04** REVOLUTIONIZE CHOREOGRAPHY by building and structuring an interactive repository of motion capture dance libraries. Custom dance data blending engine will give choreographers and dance teachers a powerful tool to blend and assemble an infinite number of dance compositions.
- 05** WIDEN THE ACCESS AND PRACTICE OF DANCE by providing access to the created dance database through commercially available consumer grade motion capture devices like the MS Kinect, Intel's real sense and others.

Wholodance has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 688865

Consortium

LYNKEUS, ATHENA, MOTEK ENTERTAINMENT, POLITECNICO MILANO 2015, Peachnote, Coventry University, UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI GENOVA, Kdanse, and a circular logo.

The Posters, two photos, and a short description of the project are also available in the Press Release section of the website, where not only Wholodance's Partners but also Journalists and Opinion Makers could easily download the content and use it to communicate the project:

1.4.5. Social Network

The twitter account is active and both graphic and video materials have been already posted. The daily activity of the account include the retweet of European Projects related to Dance and all other projects that can be of interest of the wide audience that be interested in knowing more about the project.

1.4.6. Vimeo Channel

The Premium Vimeo account for the project has been activated and has been used both for sharing video content among partners in private mode but also to share videos with the general public.

1.4.7. Publications

Throughout WhoLoDancE duration, novel developments will be submitted for publication in relevant international specialised journals and disseminated through the annual WhoLoDancE Newsletter, thus ensuring a regular update about the project's developments. The following preliminary list of selected publications will be a primary target for disseminating the outcomes of the project:

- International Journal of Music Education (ISME – International Society for Music Education)
- Musicae Scientiae (ESCOM - European Society for the Cognitive Science of Music)
- Psychology of Music (SAGE - Society for Education, Music and Psychology Research)
- Journal of New Music Research (Routledge)
- Music Perception (University of California Press)
- IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
- IEEE Multimedia Magazine
- IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
- International Journal of Human-Computer Studies
- ACM Transactions on Intelligent Interactive Systems
- SIGGRAPH ACM publications
- The Motion capture society News
- Research in Dance Education
- Journal of Dance Education
- Journal of Dance and Somatic Practices
- Choreographic Practices

- Convergence
- Journal of Dance Research

2. Exploitation

A preliminary exploitation approach was outlined in the Description of the Action, and it will serve as basis for future activities on this regard. Such an approach aims at building upon three core components/actors: the strategic exploitation seminar, the exploitation plans, and the role of the Innovation and IPR Manager.

In fact, the Strategic Exploitation Seminar, which is scheduled within M18, and which will involve all WhoLoDancE Partners, will be an important step toward the identification of the potential innovations stemming from the project, which will deserve a specific effort of analysis and business planning, both as individual exploitation initiatives and as joint exploitation ventures.

As anticipated in the DoA, the Innovation and IPR manager will play a key role in paving the way for and credible exploitation paths, supporting the partners and coordinating the Consortium activities in performing a preliminary market analysis, exploring the most suitable business model for the innovations implemented within the project, help the partners in the definition of an effective IPR management strategy, and also trying to maximise the knowledge exchange among the partners.

The results of the exploitation seminar and of all the relevant interactions and analysis, will be the basis for preparing a First Exploitation Plan by month 24 (followed by a Final Exploitation Plan at month 36).

The exploitation plans will contain both an analysis of the market and of the commercial outreach potential of the different solutions implemented during the project. A preliminary business model and a business plan for identifying the most promising exploitable results will be also provided within the Exploitation Plan, and will be refined from time to time, when the key features and possible usage of WhoLoDancE implemented innovation will become clearer.

As already explained in the DoW, different exploitation strategies will be proposed, taking into account the variety of specific interests which characterises WhoLoDancE partners, and the potential of the most commercially-g geared partners. Two parallel approaches will be followed:

- Individual plans: according to the current partners' core business and expertise, these plans will address the exploitation potential of the specific outcomes produced (and owned) by the individual partners, which will be provided with the needed business support to identify the most appropriate business model.

Global exploitation plan: this plan will take care of outlining the business case for the integrated solution which will result from the interaction and integration among the different activities of all WhoLoDancE partners. In particular, it will define different scenarios of exploitation of such a global solution, while investigating the most likely market entry roads. This joint plan will also take care of identifying target customers, markets, and a possible timeline for the full market outreach.

To maximise the effectiveness of the exploitation effort, established business development methodologies will be adopted. In particular, WhoLoDancE will adopt the Lean Launchpad Methodology, which has proven to be a rather effective methodology in increasing the chances of a successful commercialisation of the tools. The team in charge of exploitation (P1-Lynkeus) has participated to the Lean Launchpad methodology course funded by the European Commission, in the framework of two ongoing EU-funded Fp7 projects (MD-Paedegree and CARDIOPROOF).

The key features of the methodology are the process of experimentation/verification/validation of the business hypothesis and the iteration with the intended customers and end-users, replacing the usual self-referral planning and desk assumptions approach.

Correctly implemented, the Lean methodology will be of great support for both individual partners and the Consortium as a whole.

In particular, the Lean methodology seems to be suiting some of the key characteristics of WhoLoDancE, with particular regard to the foreseen interaction with a number of end users. In fact, the lean methodology fosters a learning process through iterations with end-users and customers. This process helps to define the customer's segment and the value proposition, eventually leading to the implementation of a Minimum Viable Product of which the market release is accelerated by the interactions with the relevant stakeholders.

2.1. Individual partners' exploitation plans

The basic exploitation perspectives proposed by the Individual partners within the DoW, which will serve as basis for future implementations.

Lynkeus

Lynkeus plans to expand its entrepreneurial and knowledge-broker effort in promoting innovation and research in the field of technological applications within music and dance, taking stock of the experience accrued in similarity search and in complex repository building in the area of ICT for Health

Athena RC

The WhoLoDancE repository and platform for storing and processing the multimodal content related to dance and its teaching will be built upon the principles of interoperability and reuse. ATHENA RC will explore the re-use of the content for various Research, Educational and Creativity exploitation cases. ATHENA RC will also explore the use of the Personalization algorithm and system for Whole-Body Interaction, in various different environments of Education and Cultural Heritage.

Coventry

The WhoLoDancE platform will be a core resource for the dance teaching faculty to support teaching and research. As the researchers work directly with professional dance artists and organisations the repository and platform will be widely promoted in its research- informed professional practice activities. Coventry will also feature the platform and its impact in public engagement events (conferences, symposia etc) and within publications.

Motek

When the WhoLoDancE final product is available, Motek will explore the usage of its entertainment based network in order to advance possible commercial exploitation in parallel motion driven sectors beside Dance.

Peachnote

Peachnote will examine the re-use of expressive dance gestures that are part of the WhoLoDancE repository and will explore related applications in entertainment and creativity related fields.

PoliMi

PoliMI intends to capitalize on the multimodal machine learning technology that will be developed in the form of innovative services for artistic projects, and intends to explore the possibility of developing software for the gaming industry as well as for supporting remote teaching (music and more).

Unige

Utilisation of project results in artistic projects, with the dance companies partners in the project. Exploitation of project results in the EU Culture Project MetaBody. Cross-fertilization with the EU H2020 ICT Project DANCE.

3. Management of the dissemination and exploitation activities

Dissemination and exploitation activities are under the responsibility of P1 Lynkeus (LYNK) and involve all the partners. WP8 will involve work throughout the length of the project.

In the following table, the effort for each partner is shown.

Participation per Partner

Partner number and short name	WP8 effort
1 - LYNKEUS	18.00
2 - ATHENA RC	1.00
3 - MOTEK	1.00
4 - POLIMI	1.00
5 - UNIGE	3.00
6 - Peachnote GmbH	1.00
7 - COVUNI	1.00
8 - STOCOS	2.00
9 - K. Danse	2.00
10 - LCGW	2.00
Total	32.00